

Algorithmic Transparency: Law and Policy Landscape

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Internship

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Overview

The AI Policy / Law landscape has large numbers of documents being published every few days from industry, national and international institutions (OECD, WEF, WIPO, etc). For those interested in understanding how particular topics in this landscape are evolving (for example, **algorithmic transparency**), the volume and frequency of new information makes the task insurmountable.

The idea behind this project would be for an intern to help automatically parse these documents, to get an overview of things like frequency / variability / context of use for key terms, to help visualise these in readable formats, and to potentially also support researchers by directing them to important sections of the text. Amanda Horzyk has been maintaining a listing of the sources / documents of interest and given that her work is particularly focused on algorithmic transparency that would be the main topic of inquiry for the project.

Victoria McTrusty is a 4th year MInf student (CV attached) whose project this year focused on analysing bias in video datasets. She is interested in looking at the intersection of **computing and law**, and this project has been tailored to give her the opportunity to do that while also **practicing her NLP skills** (from FNLP and MLS).

Resources

Inspiration:

- "Comparing Apples to Oranges: A Taxonomy for Navigating the Global Landscape of AI Regulation" <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2505.13673>

Landscape Overviews: AI Regulation

- CAIDP <https://www.caidp.org/reports/aidv-2025/> AIDV 2025 – p34-52 + **Introduction to the AI Policy Sourcebook.**
- State of the AI Regulatory Landscape May 2024 ([here](#))
- GPD AI Governance Landscape Mapping ([here](#)), background info: [here](#)
- State of AI Regulations in 2025: Everything you need to know: Holistic A: [access](#) (pdf [here](#))
- US Open-Source AI Governance ([here](#)) by Centre for AI Policy and Digital Ethics agency (DEC) Yale.
- Work Bank Group: Global Trends in AI Governance: *Country approaches* “World Bank Group. 2024. Global Trends in AI Governance: Evolving Country Approaches. © World Bank. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/42500>.”

Primary Documents (pre 2025):

AI ACT Resources

- **AI ACT:** <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>
- High-level Summary: <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/high-level-summary/>
- **AI Office:** AI Pact Official Webinar series
 - Webinar I: Webinar exploring the Architecture of the AI Act ([here](#))
 - Webinar II: Second Webinar on the architecture of the AI Act ([here](#))
 - Webinar III: Third AI Pact webinar on AI literacy ([here](#))
 - Webinar IV: Guidelines for Prohibited AI Practices under the AI Act and the Definition of an AI system ([here](#))
- **Gabriele Mazzini: Inside the mind of the EU AI Act architect TED Talk ([here](#))**
 - Harmonised Standards for the European AI Act, JRC Publication, Soler Garrido, J., De Nigris, S. Bassani, E., Sanchez, I., Evas, T. Andre, A, Boulange, T., Harmonised Standards for the European AI Act, European Commission, Seville, 2024, JRC139430. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC139430>
 - New Legal Framework Harmonization Legislation Cen Cenelec Standardisation ([here](#)) AI Act ([here](#))
- **AI Board Activity:**
 - AI Board convenes for its third meeting to advance EU AI policy ([here](#))
 - Operationalising the EU AI Act: webinar One Trust ([here](#))
 - AI Office; preliminary guidelines to clarify the scope of the obligations of providers of general purpose AI models in the AI Act: [here](#)

U.S. Executive Orders

- White House, Executive Order 13859, Maintaining American Leadership in Artificial Intelligence (2019)
- White House, Executive Order 13960, Promoting the Use of Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence in the Federal Government (2020)
- White House, Executive Order 14110, The Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Development and Use of Artificial Intelligence (2023)
- National Security Memorandum on AI (2024)
- **White House, Executive Order 14141, Advancing United States Leadership in Artificial Intelligence Infrastructure (2025)**
- **White House, Executive Order 14179, Removing Barriers to American Leadership in Artificial Intelligence (2025)**

Comparison: Definitions of "AI" and "AI System"

- China Electronics Standardization Institute, Artificial Intelligence Standardization White Paper (2018)
- OECD AI Principles / G20 AI Guidelines (2019, updated 2024)
- UNESCO, Recommendation on the Ethics of AI [excerpt] (2022)
- **EU AI Act, Regulation 2024/1689 (2024)**
- Council of Europe, Framework Convention on AI (2024)
- **AI Basic Act (Republic of Korea 2024)**
- An Act Concerning Consumer Protections in Interactions with Artificial Intelligence Systems (Colorado, U.S. 2024)

- White House, Executive Order 14110, The Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Development and Use of Artificial Intelligence (2023)
- White House, Executive Order 14179, Removing Barriers to American Leadership in Artificial Intelligence (2025)
- European Law Institute, The concept of ‘AI system’ under the new AI Act: Arguing for a Three-Factor Approach (2025)

AI Resources

- National Strategies & Guidelines
- International Organizations’ Statements and Reports
- Other Reports
- Organizations

International Instruments

- Public Voice, Universal Guidelines for AI (2018)
- OECD AI Principles / G20 AI Guidelines (2019, updated 2024)
- African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights, Res. 473 (2021)
- African Union, Continental AI Strategy [excerpt] (2021)
- Windhoek Statement (2022)
- UNESCO, Recommendation on the Ethics of AI [excerpt] (2022)
- Saudi Data & AI Authority, AI Ethics Principles [excerpt] (2023)
- Hiroshima Process International Guiding Principles (2023)
- The Bletchley Declaration (2023)
- Santiago Declaration (2024)
- **UN General Assembly, Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy AI for SDG (2024)**
- **UN General Assembly, International Cooperation on AI (2024)**
- Seoul Declaration (2024)
- Cartagena de Indias Declaration (2024)
- Council of Europe, Framework Convention on AI (2024)
- Declaration of Montevideo (2024)
- Vatican Guidelines on AI (2025)

Domestic Laws

- **EU AI Act, Regulation 2024/1689 (2024)**
- **Interim Measures for the Management of Generative Artificial Intelligence Services (China 2023)**
- **Directive on Automated Decision-making (Canada 2023)**
- **An Act Concerning Consumer Protections in Interactions with Artificial Intelligence Systems (Colorado, U.S. 2024)**
- **California AI Transparency Act (California, U.S. 2024)**
- **AI Basic Act (Republic of Korea 2024)**

International Instruments (2025)

- [The Africa Declaration on Artificial Intelligence \(2025\)](#)
- [The Doha Declaration on AI and Human Rights \(2025\)](#)

U.S. Executive Orders (2025)

- [Office of Management and Budget, M-25-22 Driving Efficient Acquisition of Artificial Intelligence in Government \(April 3, 2025\)](#)
- [Office of Management and Budget \(OMB\), M-25-21 Accelerating Federal Use of AI through Innovation, Governance, and Public Trust \(April 03, 2025\)](#)
 - [Fact Sheet: Eliminating Barriers for Federal Artificial Intelligence Use and Procurement \(April 3, 2025\)](#)

Databases:

AI Policy trackers

- **FAIRLY Tracker** (8th May 2025) <https://www.fairly.ai/blog/map-of-global-ai-regulations?>
- **Global AI Regulation Tracker** ([here](#)) - Raymond Sun
- AIPEX – AI Policy Exchange Forum ([here](#))
- Policy Search Database:
 - Overton: <https://app.overton.io/dashboard.php>
 - Policy Commons: <https://policycommons.net/>
- White & Case AI Watch: Global Regulatory Tracker <https://www.whitecase.com/insight-our-thinking/ai-watch-global-regulatory-tracker>
- CAIDP #ai_policy_news channel and LinkedIn News Feed ([here](#))
- GPD AI Governance Landscape Mapping ([here](#)), background info: [here](#)
- Lexology AI News: IT & IP, DPIP News <https://www.lexology.com/>
- AIPP Global AI Law and Policy Tracker ([here](#) – US Centric)
- **US AI Legislation Tracker** ([here](#))
- Tracking Federal Judge Orders On Artificial Intelligence ([here](#))
- GDPR Enforcement tracker: <https://www.enforcementtracker.com/>
- OECD Policy Tracker: <https://oecd.ai/en/> (National AI policies & strategies)
- AI Policy Portal: <https://aipolicyportal.org/>
- African AI Policy Observatory <https://policy.africanobservatory.ai/>
- Tech Policy Atlas (repository) <https://techpolicydesign.au/tech-policy-atlas>
- Tech Policy AI Act Tracker <https://www.techpolicy.press/tracker/ai-act/>; <https://www.techpolicy.press/tracker/>

- UK AI Tracker LexisNexis <https://www.lexisnexis.co.uk/legal/guidance/uk-artificial-intelligence-tracker>
- Casey Fiesler AI Ethics and Policy News Tracker ([here](#))
- Global tech law news ([here](#))
- Tracking the Trackers (Oliver Patel): ([here](#))
- AIDV AI and Democratic Values Index (<https://www.caidp.org/reports/aidv-2023/>)
- Human Rights, Democracy, and Rule of Law Impact Assessment (HUDERIA):<https://rm.coe.int/cai-bu-2022-03-outline-of-huderia-risk-and-impact-assessment-methodolo/1680a81e14>
- AI Unplugged commentary tracker ([here](#))
- Summaries of EU legislation (replaces SCAD) http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/index.htm
- Artificial Intelligence Governance Library www.aigl.blog/
 - Books, Guides, Reports, Policies, Research, Templates, Checklists, Frameworks, and even Standards

AI Legal Cases trackers

- AI Litigation Database <https://blogs.gwu.edu/law-eti/ai-litigation-database/>
- Generative AI IP case tracker <https://www.mishcon.com/generative-ai-intellectual-property-cases-and-policy-tracker>
- Status of AI copyright lawsuits ([here](#))
- News Publisher deal vs lawsuits tracker <https://pressgazette.co.uk/platforms/news-publisher-ai-deals-lawsuits-openai-google/>
- Tech Litigation Database <https://tech-litigation.com/about/>

Compliance repositories and Standards

- AI Standards Hub Europe: <https://aistandardshub.org/>
- Harmonised Standards for the European AI Act, JRC Publication, Soler Garrido, J., De Nigris, S. Bassani, E., Sanchez, I., Evas, T. Andre, A, Boulange, T., Harmonised Standards for the European AI Act, European Commission, Seville, 2024, JRC139430. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC139430>
- Accessible Guide to Standards: [here](#)
 - ISO 42001 (management system);
 - ISO 23894 (risk framework);
 - ISO 22989 (definitions);
 - ISO 23053 (life cycle map);
 - ISO 24368 (ethics and human impact);
 - ISO 38507 (governance and leadership)
 - ISO 31000 series of standards on risk management
- AI Standards: ISO/IEC 42001:2023 Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Management system <https://www.iso.org/standard/81230.html>

- o ISO 27001 – Your Information Security Management System (ISMS). Protects your data and systems.
- o ISO 27701 – Your Privacy Information Management System (PIMS). Extends 27001 to cover privacy and compliance with regulations like GDPR and CCPA.
- o ISO 42001 – Your Artificial Intelligence Management System (AIMS). The newest standard, focused on governing how you develop, deploy, and use AI responsibly.
- o ISO 23894 is the lens (It's a risk management standard made for AI, It speaks the language of modelling, bias, fairness, misuse, opacity, feedback loops and unintended outcomes)

- NIST Checklist Repository <https://ncp.nist.gov/repository>
- Assessment & Auditing Resources <https://www.nist.gov/cyberframework/assessment-auditing-resources>
- BSI Standards Library <https://knowledge.bsigroup.com/search?query=>
- EU Observatory for ICT Standards <https://www.standict.eu/standards-repository>
- ETSI Search and Browse Standards <https://www.etsi.org/standards-search#Pre-defined%20Collections>
- IEEE Standards Collections <https://innovate.ieee.org/ieee-standards-online-collections/>
 - o IEEE 7000 series –
 - ♣ IEEE 7000 – Embedding ethics into system design
 - ♣ IEEE 7001 – Transparency in autonomous systems
 - ♣ IEEE 7002 – Privacy in intelligent systems
 - ♣ IEEE 7003 – Tackling algorithmic bias
 - ♣ IEEE P7004 – Protecting children and students
 - ♣ IEEE 7005 – Transparent employer data governance
 - ♣ IEEE 7007 – Ontologies for ethical robotics
 - ♣ IEEE P7008 – Nudging vs. manipulation
 - ♣ IEEE 7009 – Fail-safe autonomous systems
 - ♣ IEEE P7009.1 – Safety interventions in autonomy
 - ♣ IEEE 7010 – Well-being by design
 - ♣ IEEE P7010.1 – ESG and AI systems
 - ♣ IEEE P7011 – Trustworthy news content
 - ♣ IEEE P7012 – Machine-readable privacy terms
 - ♣ IEEE 7014 – Ethical emulated empathy
 - ♣ IEEE P7014.1 – Empathy in general-purpose AI
 - ♣ IEEE P7015 – Data/AI literacy and readiness
 - ♣ IEEE P7016 – Metaverse governance
 - ♣ IEEE P7016.1 – Metadata for XR education
 - ♣ IEEE P7017 – Human-robot interaction
 - ♣ IEEE P7018 – Secure generative AI

- ♣ IEEE P7019 – Earth Law and AI
 - ♣ IEEE P7100 – Environmental impact of AI
 - ♣ IEEE P8000 – Ethical property specs in AI
 - Other: governance standards, including FCA, PRA, ECB, SEC, and OCC.
- IEEE 1547-2018 Adoption Tracker <https://irecusa.org/resources/ieee-1547-2018-adoption-tracker/>
 - New Legal Framework Harmonization Legislation Cen Cenelec Standardisation (here) AI Act (here)
 - EU AI Act Compliance Tracker: <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/assessment/eu-ai-act-compliance-checker/>
 - EU Strategy on Standardisation (here)
 - Cen-Cenelec (here) Areas of Work
 - AI standardisation Inclusiveness Newsletter Created within Cen-Cenelec Joint Technical Committee 21 (here) responsible for standardisation in AI
 - Visual Dashboard available (here)
 - Status Update of JTC 21 Activities in response to Standardisation Requests on AI (here) February 2024
 - Official AI Standards Hub Webinars (here)
 - Cen/CLC Published Standards (here)
 - SCL - Society for Computers and Law issued a report dedicated to the EU AI Act Contractual Clauses, October 2024 <https://www.scl.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/SCL-AI-Group-EU-AI-Act-Contractual-Clauses-13-Oct-2024.pdf>
 - Australia Voluntary AI Safety Standard, August 2024 <https://www.industry.gov.au/sites/default/files/2024-09/voluntary-ai-safety-standard.pdf>

SECONDARY DOCUMENTS:

Comparisons and Whitepapers:

- **The AI Act between Digital and Sectoral Regulations**, Bertelsmann Stiftung ([here](#)) examine how the AI Act fits into the broader regulatory ecosystem, including DSA, GDPR, as well as regulations in the finance, medical devices, and automotive sectors.

Tools, Playbooks, Matrix

- Map: Choosing the right controls for AI risks access ([here](#))
 - A systematic approach to selecting the most effective prevention, detection, and response controls for major AI risks - both human and technical and from design to operation.
- Images of AI Playbook – AixDesign ([here](#))

- Oliver Patel, AI Usage Policy Playbook (Step-by-step guide on how to write your AI Usage Policy, 20 key principles it needs to cover links and takeaways on 16 Generative AI policy case studies) ([here](#))
- Oliver Patel AI Usage Policy playbook ([here](#))
- Artificial Intelligence Playbook for the UK Government ([here](#))
- NIST AI 600-1 Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework: Generative Artificial Intelligence Profile ([here](#))
- OECD Trustworthy AI Metrics <https://oecd.ai/en/catalogue/metrics>
- OECD Catalogue of Tools for Trustworthy AI <https://oecd.ai/en/catalogue/tools>
- MIT, boomi, A playbook for crafting AI strategy “to meet their AI ambitions organizations must shift from pilots and experiments to enterprise-wide deployment” ([access](#))
- Rwanda, AI Playbook For Small States, ([access](#))
- India, Responsible AI Developers Playbook, ([access](#))
- Singapore, Public Sector with Comprehensive AI Playbook ([access](#))
- PwC on Agentic AI, Playbook ([access](#))
- Google, The Chief Artificial Intelligence Officer Playbook: A Practical Guide ([access](#)) for Public Sector
- OneTrust AI playbook: An actionable guide ([access](#))
- UK Gov, Defence Artificial Intelligence (AI) Playbook ([access](#))
- US Gov, DOE AI Risk Management Playbook (AIRMP) ([access](#))
- McKinsey, The executive’s AI playbook ([access](#))
- NIST AI RMF Playbook ([access](#)), overview ([here](#))
 - 5 AI RMF Core ([here](#))
- Credo AI, RAI Parent Playbook: Your Step-by-Step Guide to Responsible AI ([access](#))
- World Economic Forum, Responsible AI Playbook for Investors ([access](#))
- PEAT The Equitable AI Playbook ([access](#)), 1-pager explanation ([here](#))
- GSMA, The AI Ethics Playbook Implementing ethical principles into everyday business, 2022 ([access](#))
- Snowflake, The Data Governance Playbook for AI in Healthcare On-Demand ([video](#))
- Microsoft AI Playbook - provides enterprise software engineers with solutions, capabilities, and code developed to solve real-world AI problems ([website](#))
- AI In Global Development Playbook USAID Gov (is published pursuant to Section 11(c)(i) of the United States Executive Order on the Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Development and Use of Artificial Intelligence) ([access](#))
- Alation Healthcare Whitepaper 4.23.24, The Healthcare Data Governance Playbook: Fast Tracking AI Success 2024 ([access](#)), alternative link ([here](#))
- Berkeley, Playbook for Product Managers & Business Leaders for AI Governance ([here](#)), article ([here](#))

On Responsible AI (Further reading)

Papers

- When Is a Decision Automated? A Taxonomy for a Fundamental Rights Analysis, Francesca Palmiotto ([access](#))
- Replication Data for: The Many Shades of Impact Assessments, Pierre Dewitte KU Leuven Centre for IT & IP Law ([access](#)), kuleuven repository ([access](#))
- A Regulatory Roadmap to AI and Privacy Daniel Solove, GWU Law School Public Law Research Paper Forthcoming ([here](#))
- Umut Turksen. *Ethics in AI and Surveillance Research*. CRISP Seminar Series No.4. 10 November 2023.
 - Trace Questions ([here](#))

Books

- Oxford Handbook of the Foundations and Regulation of Generative AI ([here](#))
- Artificial Intelligence in Byte-sized Chunks Peter J. Bentley ([here](#))
- The Ethics of Artificial Intelligence: Principles, Challenges, and Opportunities by Prof Luciano Floridi ([amazon](#))
- Olivia Gambelin on Responsible AI ([access](#))
- Christoph Stückelberger, AI governance ethics: artificial intelligence with shared values and rules ([online access](#))
- Christoph Stückelberger, Accountability through integrity : toward a balanced education ([online access](#))
- Shannon Vallor The AI Mirror: How to Reclaim our Humanity in an Age of Machine Thinking ([online access](#))
- Can We Move Fast Without Breaking Things? Software Engineering Methods Matter to Human Rights Outcomes Alexander Voss ([link](#))
- Atlas of AI Power, Politics, and the Planetary Costs of Artificial Intelligence Kate Crawford ([online access](#))
- Automating Inequality : How High-Tech Tools Profile, Police, and Punish the Poor Virginia Eubanks ([physical access library](#))
- Algorithms of Oppression Safiya Noble ([online access](#))
- Tragic Design: The Impact of Bad Product Design and How to Fix It (Book by Cynthia Savard Saucier and Jonathan Shariat) ([online access](#))
- Your Computer Is on Fire (Mullaney, Thomas S) ([online access](#))
- Race after technology : abolitionist tools for the new Jim code by Benjamin Ruha ([online access](#))
- The Age of Surveillance Capitalism ([S Zuboff](#))
- Coded Bias <https://www.codedbias.com/>
- The Smart Wife: Why Siri, Alexa, and Other Smart Home Devices Need a Feminist Reboot <https://mitpress.mit.edu/9780262542791/the-smart-wife/>

- [Inventing Accuracy: A Historical Sociology of Nuclear Missile Guidance \(Inside Technology\) Donald MacKenzie 1993](#)

Explainability: Legal Considerations and Seminal Works (Further Reading)

- XAI in Education European Commission report, access ([here](#)): Fostering human oversight and shared responsibility.
- "A Legal Framework for eXplainable AI," by Aniket Kesari, Dr. Daniela Sele, Elliott Ash & Stefan Bechtold, Working Paper <https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch/handle/20.500.11850/699762>
- Lisboa, P.J., Saralajew, S., Vellido, A., Fernández-Domenech, R. and Villmann, T., 2023. [The coming of age of interpretable and explainable machine learning models. *Neurocomputing*, 535, pp.25-39.](#)
- The Role of Explainable AI in the Research Field of AI Ethics Authors: Heidi Vainio-Pekka et al. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3599974>

Preceding and Seminal work, and workbooks

- Alan Turing AI Explainability in Practice ('AI Ethics and Governance in Practice Programme') Workbook <https://www.turing.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2024-06/aieg-ati-7-explainabilityv1.2.pdf>
- Alan Turing, Best Practice Document, Challenges and Gaps in AI Explainability
 - ICO Explaining Decisions with AI <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/artificial-intelligence/explaining-decisions-made-with-artificial-intelligence/>
 - Workbook Use Case 1: Explaining decisions made with AI: A workbook (Use case 1: AI-assisted recruitment tool) <https://zenodo.org/records/4624711#.YUiUzy1Q1ao>
 - Workbook Use Case 2: Explaining decisions made with AI: A workbook (Use case 2: Machine learning for children's social care) <https://zenodo.org/records/4624733#.YUiVAy1Q1ao>
 - Insights from phase two of Project ExplAIIn Phase 2 Outcomes <https://www.turing.ac.uk/news/project-explain/insights-from-phase-two>
- David Gunning et al. XAI—Explainable artificial intelligence. *Sci. Robot.* 4, eaay7120(2019). [DOI:10.1126/scirobotics.aay7120](https://doi.org/10.1126/scirobotics.aay7120)
- Todd Kulesza, Margaret Burnett, Weng-Keen Wong, and Simone Stumpf. 2015. Principles of Explanatory Debugging to Personalize Interactive Machine Learning. In *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces (IUI '15)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 126–137. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2678025.2701399>

- Goebel, R. *et al.* (2018). Explainable AI: The New 42?. In: Holzinger, A., Kieseberg, P., Tjoa, A., Weippl, E. (eds) Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction. CD-MAKE 2018. Lecture Notes in Computer Science(), vol 11015. Springer, Cham.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99740-7_21
 - A. Bussone, S. Stumpf and D. O'Sullivan, "The Role of Explanations on Trust and Reliance in Clinical Decision Support Systems," [2015 International Conference on Healthcare Informatics, Dallas, TX, USA, 2015, pp. 160-169, doi: 10.1109/ICHI.2015.26.](#)
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Clinic: <https://www.caidp.org/global-academic-network/ai-policy-clinic/>
<https://www.caidp.org/resources/ai-policy-sourcebook/>
<https://www.caidp.org/reports/aidv-2025/>

CHAPTER 1

THE EU'S APPROACH TO ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE GOVERNANCE

1. The European Union Artificial Intelligence Act

The European Union AI Act, the first-ever legal framework on Artificial Intelligence (AI), entered into force on August 1st, 2024. This horizontal regulation applies to all AI systems whether or not it is embedded into another product or used independently. To create an internal market for safe and trustworthy AI along the entire value chain, it establishes three overarching objectives of:

This ~~influential~~ legal framework encourages AI developers and deployers to innovate; by reducing liability risks through legal certainty. It provides particular support mechanisms for smaller players to compete through standardisation of legislative requirements, allowances and regulatory sandboxes to assist with compliance. However, predominantly, it shapes mechanisms to help enforce fundamental rights and obligations, complementing various existing EU laws (e.g., sectoral regulations, product safety legislation); across all sectors. High-level requirements enshrined in the AI Act are supported by technical standards, while tapping into existing but tailored conformity procedures with an AI-specific layer.

The AI Act follows the well-established New Legislative Framework Approach used since late 1980s by the Commission for product safety regulations with both ex-ante and ex-post requirements and checks. There are two key bodies overseeing and supporting the implementation of the Act beyond Member States, the [AI Office](#) and the [AI Board](#):

The European AI Office

- Central organ supporting the **coherent implementation and application of the AI Act** across member states
- **Operates within the European Commission** but has its own structure, the office combines expertise on AI regulation, AI safety, innovation, and policy coordination.
- **Regulates general-purpose AI models**, provides technical support and coordinates with national authorities.

The European AI Board

- An advisory group composed of **high-level representatives from EU member states**
- **Brings all stakeholders together to discuss a harmonized approach** to interpreting and applying the legislation
- **Advises the AI Office on policy, strategy, and implementation**, coordinates supervisory activities among member states, harmonises enforcement and ensures consistent application of the AI Act

The AI Act employs a four-tier system, with a pyramid of risk, which regulates only as much and as far as required by the risk (see **Figure 1**). Technical standards are being developed by European Standardisation Organisations to ensure operational clarity for providers and deployers. Technical standards were requested in spring 2024 and are expected in 2025. 💬

Figure 1: Four-tier Pyramid of Risk, AI Office, AI Pact Webinar 1, 28 November 2024 ([access](#))

The Act took effect on **1st August 2024**, but provisions apply gradually until **1st August 2027**:

- **February 2025:** Prohibitions become enforceable. AI literacy obligations enter into force.
- **August 2025:** General-purpose AI model rules start, by then we will have a code of practice.
- **August 2026:** High-risk self-standing AI systems in Annex III must comply with technical and procedural requirements.
- **August 2027:** AI embedded in regulated products (e.g., medical devices, machinery) must fully comply with the AI Act (Annex I)

Providers of AI-Systems

- Establish a risk and quality management systems
- Comply with data governance requirements
- Draw up technical documentation
- Design high risk AI systems for record-keeping
- Ensure compliance with requirements regarding human oversight
- Provide instructions for use to downstream deployers
- Design to achieve appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity
- Register system in central EU high-risk AI database, report incidents, cooperate with supervisory authorities

Am I a “Provider”? A provider is a natural or legal person marketing an AI system under their trade name (potentially not the original developer if they market it, rebrand or distribute it). For instance, those who develop or place the system on the market, such as a developer of an AI recruitment screening tool for HR.

Deployers of AI-Systems

- Abide by the provider’s instructions for use, including training staff to oversee AI correctly
- Deploy System only on representative data aligned with the intended design
- In the **Public Sector**? First carry out the fundamental rights impact assessment!

Am I a “Deployer”? Deployers are those who *use* the system. It can be an entity, public or private, that buys and uses or integrates the AI system under its authority (for instance, an HR department employing an AI-driven recruitment tool).

The AI Office oversees a comprehensive engagement plan known as the AI Pact allowing organisations to engage with the Commission and other stakeholders to share best practices and join activities such as the AI Pact Events (including monthly thematic webinars, tailored workshops, and public consultations). The aim of this approach is to support businesses in planning ahead of the full implementation of the AI Act and establish an open policy dialogue on AI under the European AI

Alliance initiative.

This playbook, however, treats the AI Act as just one source of ethical principles that are now enshrined in European law. It seeks to offer a pathway to holistic ethical and responsible AI approaches that move beyond compliance.